

Redundant parallel beam multi-axis force sensor – Force calibration with traceability

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Abstract—Because the orthogonality of standard forces and torques cannot be guaranteed, the traceability chain of the conventional multi-axis force calibration is broken. The error sphere is proposed in this paper to define the multi axis force and torque error. The force calibration with traceability can be realized using the force error sphere. The force adjustment objective function is further proposed, which can be employed in the optimization to solve the observable variable stiffness matrix. The force adjustment objective function includes the force magnitude objective function and the force coordinate system objective function. The force angle error and the frictional force error is the main error sources, which contribute to a large force error in the conventional calibration, which have a low impact on the magnitude of the standard force. Only the magnitude of the standard force is employed in this paper's calibration and adjustment. Therefore, an unbroken traceability chain can be guaranteed. The simulation results show that the force observable variable stiffness matrix adjusted using this paper's method is nearly identical to the matrix adjusted using the conventional method.

Index Terms—Standard, Calibration, Adjustment, Traceability chain, Error sphere/ellipsoid, Objective function, Optimization

Notation: Objective function name

$funF_x^{M,n}$

- **Auxiliary function name:** F -Caused by force; M -Caused by torque; FM -Caused by both force and torque;
- **Number of standard force and torque:** n ;
- **Main function name:** F -Force function; M -Torque function; FM -Force and torque relation function
- **Direction of force or torque:** x, y, z -Along or about $x, y,$ or z axis; xy, yz, zx -In $xy, yz,$ or zx plane; Blank-In the space including both $x, y,$ and z ;

I. Introduction

MAFS (Multi-axis force sensor) is one of the most important sensors used in robotics, aerospace, bionics, wind/water tunnel balance, rocket/water jet engine thrust testing, machining, and automobile testing etc. [1-6].

The calibration and adjustment of the MAFS is an important content in the multi-axis force measurement. Conventionally, a so-called ideal six axis force source was usually employed in the calibration/adjustment. A MAFS can be calibrated/adjusted using three methods. The first method was that the MAFS is calibrated using a standard MAFS [7-20]. However, the standard MAFS still needs a more accurate calibration. The second method was that the MAFS is calibrated using multiple uniaxial force sensors/actuators [21-37]. The third method was using multiple standard weights [38-63]. However, the orthogonality of these standard calibration loads can hardly be

guaranteed in the last two methods. The orthogonality of the calibration mechanics was mentioned in some studies [64], in fact, even the orthogonality of the structure can be guaranteed, because of the uneven distribution of the stress and the frictional force, the orthogonality of the six-axis force is still not good enough. Therefore, the error of the so-called ideal six axis force source itself is relatively big, so for a high accuracy MAFS, the conventional calibration/adjustment method is not suitable.

Although some MAFS standards/specifications were proposed [65,66], only the adjustment of the inner parameters of a MAFS was detailed in these standards/specifications, the calibration of the MAFS and the traceability of the so-called ideal six axis force source (stated reference) were always avoided to be mentioned. These standards/specifications were more like the inner adjustment documents of an enterprise only.

It was always expected to find an ideal six axis force source as a stated reference in conventional study. However, at least up to now, the ideal six axis force source does not exist.

The coordinate measurement machine (CMM) was used to measure the length and angle vector in 6D space. Similarly, no suitable ideal six-axis length/angle source exists for the calibration of an CMM. Therefore, a series of standards were proposed for the calibration of CMM [67-72]. These standards are the perfect references for the standard establishment of the MAFS.

In this paper, the error sphere is proposed for the force calibration procedure. In the calibration, only the magnitude of the standard force is required. Therefore, the traceability of such a force calibration can be guaranteed. A force adjustment

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calculation is further proposed in which the force magnitude objective function and the force coordinate system objective function are employed.

II. CONVENTIONAL ERROR EXPRESSION IN THE MULTI-AXIS FORCE MEASUREMENT

Fig. 1. Error and crosstalk in the conventional calibration using standard orthogonal forces and torques.

Conventionally, the accuracy of a multi-axis force sensor can be evaluated using error (or class I error) and crosstalk (or class II error, dimensional coupling, cross coupling). As shown in Fig. 1 (a), the standard force is applied along the x axis, the error refers to the deviation between the measured force and the standard force along the x axis, the crosstalk refers to the deviation along the other axes and about the x , y , and z axes respectively.

TABLE I

CONVENTIONAL EXPRESSION OF STANDARD ORTHOGONAL LOADS ALONG WITH ERROR AND CROSTALK FOR A MAFS, FS—FULL SCALE

Load set	Standard load (theoretical true value)						Measurements					
	F_x (FS)	F_y (FS)	F_z (FS)	M_x (FS)	M_y (FS)	M_z (FS)	F_x (FS)	F_y (FS)	F_z (FS)	M_x (FS)	M_y (FS)	M_z (FS)
1	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	99.8%	1.2%	2.3%	1.7%	2.6%	2.9%
2	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2.2%	100.1%	1.8%	2.9%	1.9%	2.4%
3	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%	2.6%	1.7%	99.7%	2.1%	1.5%	1.9%
4	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	1.8%	1.3%	2.8%	100.5%	2.0%	1.8%
5	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	1.5%	1.8%	2.5%	1.7%	99.4%	2.4%
6	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	2.3%	1.3%	2.5%	2.3%	2.6%	99.3%

Orthogonality of the standard loads in 6D space.

Usually, the error and crosstalk can be expressed as that shown in TABLE I. When the standard force along axis x , $F_x = 100\%FS$, the force along the other axes and the torque about all the three axes caused by the standard force are $0\%FS$. As shown in Fig. 1 (b), the above definition indicates that the three standard forces along every axis should be perpendicular to each other, and all of them should go through one intersection point, the three standard torques about every axis should be parallel to corresponding forces. In other words, the three forces and three torques should be orthogonal to each other in six-dimensional space. Besides, the scale of the force and the torque should be uniformed. Thus, this standard load is called as an ideal six axis force source. The measurement experiments should be carried out based on such a standard load. The above condition of a standard load affects the calibration of a MAFS significantly. Therefore, all these conditions must be traceable.

III. ORTHOGONALITY OF THE CONVENTIONAL STANDARD FORCES AND TORQUES

Fig. 2. Conventional calibration/adjustment method of the multi-axis force sensor.

As shown in Fig. 2, conventionally, a MAFS can be calibrated using three methods. The first method is that the MAFS is calibrated using a standard MAFS. However, the standard MAFS still needs a more accurate calibration. The second method is that the MAFS is calibrated using multiple uniaxial force sensors. The third method is using multiple standard weights.

Fig. 3. Misalignment of the equivalent force and the axial line.

As shown in Fig. 3, because of the uneven distribution of stress and the frictional force, the equivalent force can hardly be perfectly aligned with the axial line. Therefore, even the mechanical structures in Fig. 2 can be perfectly orthogonal, the six-axis force is still hard to be perfectly orthogonal, let alone that the orthogonality of the mechanical structure in 6D space itself is very difficult.

Fig. 4. Broken traceability chain in the conventional standard.

As shown in Fig. 4, generally, the traceability of the magnitude of a force or a torque is easy, however, the traceability of the orthogonality of these forces and torques can hardly be guaranteed. Therefore, the traceability chain of the conventional multi-axis force calibration is actually broken with regard of the orthogonality.

IV. ERROR SPHERE

Fig. 5. Error sphere/ellipsoid of a space vector.

Usually, an error sphere can be used to define the error of a space vector. As shown in Fig. 5 (a), an error vector is the deviation from the true vector to the practical measured vector, an error sphere indicates the smallest sphere including all the possible error vectors. The sphere can be obtained by the least square method or the minimum coverage area method. The radius of the error sphere, R_e , is the maximum measurement error. If the errors along every axis are considerably different in a specific coordinate system, an error ellipsoid can be employed to represent the error space. As shown in Fig. 5 (b), in a practical measurement, the magnitude of a space vector is usually easily obtained, then, apply the vector with a standard magnitude in any position and any posture, the error vector is the deviation between the measured magnitude and the standard magnitude along the vector. These error vectors are employed to constitute the error sphere or ellipsoid.

Fig. 6. Calibration of the length error in space for a coordinate measurement machine.

As shown in Fig. 6, the length (measurement) error of a coordinate measuring machine (CMM) is usually calibrated using gauge blocks which can be traced to other existing standards. [68]

The gauge blocks are placed randomly in any position and posture. The error vector is the deviation between the measured length and the true length of the gauge block along the gauge

block. The error vector can be in any direction in the space. Because the calibration is only based on the length of the gauge blocks, the traceability of the calibration can be guaranteed.

V. CALIBRATION OF THE MULTI-AXIS FORCE SENSOR

Both the force error and the torque error of a MAFS can be expressed using an error sphere. Accordingly, in 6D space, the error of a general 6D force can also be expressed as an 6D error sphere or ellipsoid.

(a) Conventional calibration

(b) Calibration with traceability

Fig. 7. Calibration of a MAFS.

As shown in Fig. 7, since the orthogonality of the standard loads can hardly be guaranteed, if the calibration is only depended on the magnitude of the standard load, such a calibration conforms to the definition of the error sphere, and the traceability of the calibration can be easily guaranteed. Then the radius of the error sphere can be employed as the error of a MAFS.

VI. CALIBRATION, TRACEABILITY AND ADJUSTMENT

Calibration means comparing the measured value displayed by a measuring device to the "true" reference value (standard or stated reference). Calibration involves documenting the measured error (accuracy), calculating the measuring uncertainty and producing a calibration certificate. Calibrations take place under accurately defined reference conditions, without any need for technical intervention in the device.

Traceability of measurement requires the establishment of an unbroken chain of comparisons to stated references ("true" reference) each with a stated uncertainty.

Adjustment refers to setting the measured value displayed by an instrument so that it exhibits the minimum possible deviation from the "true" reference value (stated reference).

Usually, the procedure to get the error sphere is for/about the calibration, the procedure to get the inner parameters (observable variable stiffness matrix, hereinafter referred to as stiffness matrix) of a MAFS is for/about the adjustment. The calibration needs a traceable standard force (stated reference), the standard force should be traced to some other standards with an unbroken chain. The adjustment force is better to be identical to the calibration standard force to realize an accurate adjustment.

Generally, the calibration procedure should be stated in the standard; the adjustment procedure can be decided by the

manufactures. Certainly, the adjustment is a reference of the standard, the standard is the basis of the adjustment.

Fig. 8. Calibration certificate.

Picture is from the website <https://calibrationselect.co.uk/general/calibration-or-adjustment/>, and revised.

The calibration certificate procedure is shown in Fig. 8. Strictly, the most conventional “calibration” in Fig. 2 should be called “adjustment” rather than “calibration”.

For example, in Fig. 6, the measurement using the gauge blocks with a standard length is called “calibration”, the calculation of the inner parameters of the CMM itself is the “adjustment”. The calibration procedure is the comparison with a stated reference (gauge blocks), the inner parameter of a CMM is not taken into account in the calibration procedure. However, ① the calibration should fully reflect the possible errors, for example, the gauge blocks cannot be only placed along one direction; ② the stated reference in the adjustment should be as consistent as possible with the stated reference in the calibration, in other words, it is best that the inner parameters of a sensor can be adjusted using the identical stated reference used in the calibration, certainly, only the stated reference is usually not sufficient for an adjustment.

VII. ADJUSTMENT OF AN IDEAL MULTI-AXIS FORCE SENSOR

Although the inner parameters of a MAFS are not taken into account in the calibration of the MAFS, it should be taken into account in the adjustment of a MAFS that whether the MAFS can be adjusted only using the standard loads with standard magnitude. Otherwise, the inner parameters of the MAFS can hardly be sufficiently precise.

An ideal MAFS (with rigid loading & supporting platforms or all the external loads are relevant loads) indicates that the stiffness matrix is a constant matrix. It is employed in this paper to discuss the adjustment procedure.

According to equation (17) in Paper 2[2],

$${}^g_o Q = {}^g_o s {}^g_o \Delta = {}^g_o s \left([a]^T [a] \right)^{-1} [a]^T \delta = {}^g_o S \delta, \quad (1)$$

then,

$$[{}^g_o Q^n] = {}^g_o S [{}^g_o \delta^n], \quad (2)$$

where, the number of the observable variables is m , the number of the loading samples is n . m should be no less than 6 (for a planar MAFS, $m \geq 3$), n should be no less than m , then,

$${}^g_o S = [{}^g_o Q^n] [{}^g_o \delta^n]^{-T} \left([{}^g_o \delta^n] [{}^g_o \delta^n]^{-T} \right)^{-1}. \quad (3)$$

The above equation is used in the conventional adjustment calculation of a MAFS. All the components along & about the three axes of ${}^g_o Q^n$ must be accurately known in advance. The orthogonality of these forces and torques must be guaranteed.

The adjustment method with only the magnitude of the standard force and torque is discussed below.

The stiffness matrix is,

$${}^g_o S = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & \cdots & S_{1m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ S_{61} & \cdots & S_{6m} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Then, the components of ${}^g_o Q^n$ can be expressed as,

$${}^g_o F_x^n = S_{11} \delta_1^n + \cdots + S_{1m} \delta_m^n \quad (a)$$

$${}^g_o F_y^n = S_{21} \delta_1^n + \cdots + S_{2m} \delta_m^n \quad (b)$$

$${}^g_o F_z^n = S_{31} \delta_1^n + \cdots + S_{3m} \delta_m^n \quad (c)$$

$${}^g_o M_x^n = S_{41} \delta_1^n + \cdots + S_{4m} \delta_m^n \quad (d)$$

$${}^g_o M_y^n = S_{51} \delta_1^n + \cdots + S_{5m} \delta_m^n \quad (e)$$

$${}^g_o M_z^n = S_{61} \delta_1^n + \cdots + S_{6m} \delta_m^n \quad (f)$$

These components can be employed to establish the objective functions for solving the parameters in the stiffness matrix.

Fig. 9. Establishment of the force coordinate system by the standard forces.

As shown in Fig. 9, a series of standard forces are employed in the adjustment.

A. Force/Torque magnitude objective function

The force magnitude objective function is,

$$funF^{F,n}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{3m}) = ({}^g_o F_x^n)^2 + ({}^g_o F_y^n)^2 + ({}^g_o F_z^n)^2 - ({}^g_o F^{nC})^2 = 0, \quad (6)$$

where ${}^g_o F^{nC}$ indicates the standard calibration force.

The torque magnitude objective function is,

$$funM^{M,n}(S_{41}, \dots, S_{6m}) = ({}^g_o M_x^n)^2 + ({}^g_o M_y^n)^2 + ({}^g_o M_z^n)^2 - ({}^g_o M^{nC})^2 = 0, \quad (7)$$

where ${}^g_o M^{nC}$ indicates the standard calibration torque.

B. Force coordinate system objective function

The standard calibration forces are employed to define a unique force global coordinate system as shown in Fig. 9.

Condition 1: x axis is coincident with the 1st standard force, ${}^g_o F^{1C}$;

Condition 2: z axis is coincident with the common perpendicular of the 1st standard force, ${}^g_o F^{1C}$, and the 2nd standard force, ${}^g_o F^{2C}$, the origin of the global coordinate system is the intersection of the x axis and the z axis.

According to condition 1, the force coordinate system objective functions are,

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{fun}F_x^{F,1}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{1m}) &= {}^gF_x^1 - {}^gF^{1C} = 0 \quad (\text{a}) \\
\text{fun}F_y^{F,1}(S_{21}, \dots, S_{2m}) &= {}^gF_y^1 = 0 \quad (\text{b}) \\
\text{fun}F_z^{F,1}(S_{31}, \dots, S_{3m}) &= {}^gF_z^1 = 0 \quad (\text{c}) \\
\text{fun}M_x^{F,1}(S_{41}, \dots, S_{4m}) &= {}^gM_x^1 = 0 \quad (\text{d}) \\
\text{fun}M_y^{F,1}(S_{51}, \dots, S_{5m}) &= {}^gM_y^1 = 0 \quad (\text{e}) \\
\text{fun}M_z^{F,1}(S_{61}, \dots, S_{6m}) &= {}^gM_z^1 = 0 \quad (\text{f})
\end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

According to condition 2, the force coordinate system objective functions are,

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,2}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{2n}) &= ({}^gF_x^2)^2 + ({}^gF_y^2)^2 - (F^{2C})^2 = 0 \quad (\text{a}) \\
\text{fun}F_z^{F,2}(S_{31}, \dots, S_{3n}) &= {}^gF_z^2 = 0 \quad (\text{b}) \cdot (9) \\
\text{fun}M_z^{F,2}(S_{61}, \dots, S_{6n}) &= {}^gM_z^2 = 0 \quad (\text{c})
\end{aligned}$$

C. Relationship between the force coordinate system and the torque coordinate system

Fig. 10. Difference between the force coordinate system and the torque coordinate system.

As shown in Fig. 10, although the above objective functions can guarantee that the origin of the torque coordinate system is consistent with the origin of the force coordinate system, the posture of the two coordinate systems is inconsistent. Besides, applying a standard torque is more complex than a standard force. Therefore, only the force calibration and adjustment are discussed in this paper. It means that only the parameters, $S_{11} \sim S_{3m}$ in equation (4) are adjusted in this paper.

VIII. APPLICATION OF THE STANDARD FORCE WITH STANDARD MAGNITUDE IN THE CALIBRATION AND ADJUSTMENT

As discussed above, the standard force with standard magnitude is important in the calibration and adjustment. Therefore, the traceability and application of the standard force should be further detailed.

Fig. 11. Effect of the angle error on the calibration force, mg and F^C are the calibration force, F^A is the actual adjustment force.

As shown in Fig. 11, the calibration force is a force traceable to a stated reference. The actual adjustment force imposed on the MAFS is used to calculate the parameters of the MAFS. Usually, the closer the actual adjustment force is to the calibration force, the better. The magnitude of the force error caused by the angle error and the frictional force should be further discussed and compared with that of the conventional calibration.

A. Force error caused by the angle error

As shown in Fig. 11, let the frictional force to be zero, the adjustment forces are,

$$\begin{aligned}
F^A &= F^C = mg \quad \text{in (a)} \\
F^A &= F^C / \cos(\beta) \quad \text{in (b)} \\
F^A &= F^C \sin(\alpha) / \cos(\beta) \quad \text{in (c)}
\end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

As shown in Fig. 11 (a), under the calibration method proposed in this paper, the calibration force error caused by the angle error of the rope is,

$$eF_1^C = F^C \left| 1 - \frac{1}{\cos(\beta)} \right|. \quad (11)$$

The force error along axis y (Crosstalk) in the conventional study is,

$$eF_2^C = F^C |\sin(\beta)| \quad (12)$$

Because only the force error along axis y is relatively big, it is employed to represent the whole force error.

Fig. 12. Standard force error in the calibration.

Normalize the standard force as, $mg = F^C = 1$. The standard force error in the calibration caused by the angle error of the pressure head is as shown in Fig. 12. Although the angle error cannot be eliminated, usually, the angle error can be guaranteed to be small enough. For example, the angle error is 1° , the force error is 1.8% in the conventional calibration, it is unsuitable for a precise calibration, however, the force error is only 0.015% with the new method proposed in this paper.

With the calibration method proposed in this paper, the calibration force errors in Fig. 11 (b) and (c) are,

$$eF_3^C = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad (13)$$

$$eF_4^C = F^C \left| 1 - \frac{\cos(\alpha)}{\cos(\beta)} \right|. \quad (14)$$

The force error in Fig. 11 (b) is zero, the force amplitude error in Fig. 11 (c) is minimal where the angle errors (errors of α and β) are on a low level, such as 0° to 1° .

B. Force error caused by frictional force

Fig. 13. Affection of frictional force to calibration force.

The frictional force is another influence factor. It is within the range of, $F^f \in \{0, F^C \sin(\beta)\}$, where β is the frictional angle.

When the frictional force reaches the maximum value,

$$F_{\max}^f = F^C \sin(\beta), \text{ then,}$$

$$F^A = F^\perp \cos(\beta) + F_{\max}^f \sin(\beta) = F^\perp \cos(\beta) + F^C \sin^2(\beta), \quad (15)$$

$$F^\perp = F^C \cos(\beta). \quad (16)$$

$$F_{\min}^A = \left((F^\perp)^2 + (F_{\max}^f)^2 \right)^{1/2} = F^C. \quad (17)$$

When the frictional force reaches the minimum value, 0, then,

$$F^C = F^\perp \cos(\beta), \quad (18)$$

$$F_{\max}^C = F^\perp = F^C / \cos(\beta). \quad (19)$$

Therefore, when $F^C \sin(\beta) \geq F^f \geq 0$,

$$F^C \leq eF^C \leq F^C / \cos(\beta). \quad (20)$$

Then, with the calibration method proposed in this paper, the error caused by the frictional force is,

$$eF_3^C = F^C \left| 1 - \frac{1}{\cos(\beta)} \right|. \quad (21)$$

The frictional force is simply employed to represent the force error (crosstalk) in the conventional calibration,

$$eF_4^C = F^C |\sin(\beta)|. \quad (22)$$

The figure of equation (21) and (22) is similar with Fig. 12. The force amplitude error caused by both the angle error and the frictional force error is minimal.

IX. DISCUSSION OF THE MULTI-AXIS FORCE CALIBRATION AND ADJUSTMENT

Since the ideal six axis force source does not exist, usually some individual indicators can be employed as the stated reference to carry out the evaluation by the statistics. For example, for facial recognition, a series of individual indicators (Eye spacing, Nose height etc.) can be employed for the recognition. The force calibration/adjustment of a MAFS is to minimize the sum of deviations between the magnitude of the standard force and the magnitude of the measured force in statistics.

The adjustment of an ideal MAFS is relatively simple. For the adjustment of an actual distributed multi axis forces sensing system, more inner parameters should be adjusted using more calibration forces. In fact, most optimization methods in the big data processing or in statistics are valuable for the multi axis force adjustment. Although the existing multi-axis force sensor optimization methods [15, 73-77] are usually unsuitable for real-time calculation, they are suitable for adjustment

calculation.

The magnitude of a force can be easily traced, then it is a suitable individual indicator for the calibration and adjustment of a MAFS. According to the adjustment method proposed in this paper, multiple forces with a traceable magnitude along various direction can be employed to calculate the force stiffness matrix correctly. Further, it also proves that these forces can be employed in the force calibration.

Without the consideration of the accuracy space, the global coordinate system can be set up anywhere, only for the convenience of calculation, it is defined by two imposed forces.

In the viewpoint of statistics, the adjustment in this paper is to find a suitable coordinate system and a suitable stiffness matrix to minimize the sum of the all the deviations between the magnitude of the calibration force and the magnitude of the calculated force using the adjusted stiffness matrix in the adjusted coordinate system. Therefore, the probability that the adjusted stiffness matrix is the true stiffness matrix is relatively high. Usually, the greater the number of calibration forces is, the higher the probability is, certainly, the more complex the adjustment calculation is.

X. SIMULATION

Fig. 14. Adjustment of ideal MAFSs.

A planar model and a 3D model are used to illustrate the calibration method proposed in this paper, as shown in Fig. 14. The load is imposed on a fixed loading zone (no loading offset), then the stiffness matrix is a constant matrix.

As shown in Fig. 14 (a), the force stiffness matrix (the first two rows of the stiffness) of the planar model is adjusted using both of the conventional adjustment method and this paper proposed adjustment method. In order to avoid any ambiguities when solving the inverse solution, three observable variables, $\delta_1 \sim \delta_3$, are employed in the calculation. Certainly, more observable variables are allowed in the adjustment, usually, the objective functions with more observable variables are more complex.

TABLE II
CONDITIONS IN THE ADJUSTMENT OF THE PLANAR MODEL

Force No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Condition in conventional adjustment	$F_x(N)$	10.0	10c(60°)	10c(45°)	10c(45°)	10c(75°)	10c(75°)	10c(30°)	10c(30°)	10c(15°)
	$F_y(N)$	0.0	10s(60°)	10s(45°)	10s(45°)	10s(75°)	10s(75°)	10s(30°)	10s(30°)	10s(15°)
	$M_z(Nm)$	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
Objective function No.	1~2 a-b	3 c	4 d	5 e	6 f	7 g	8 h	9 i	10 j	
Condition in this paper's adjustment	$F(N)$	$F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$	$ F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$	$ F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$
	$M(Nm)$	$F_y = 0$	$F_z = 0$							

s: sin; c: cos;

Ten objective functions are employed in the adjustment.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{fun}F_x^{F,1}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{13}) &= {}^g F_x^{F,1} - 10 = 0 & (a) \\
 \text{fun}F_y^{F,1}(S_{21}, \dots, S_{23}) &= {}^g F_y^{F,1} = 0 & (b) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,2}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,2})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,2})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (c) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,3}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,3})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,3})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (d) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,4}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,4})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,4})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (e) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,5}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,5})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,5})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (f) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,6}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,6})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,6})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (g) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,7}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,7})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,7})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (h) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,8}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,8})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,8})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (i) \\
 \text{fun}F_{xy}^{F,9}(S_{11}, \dots, S_{23}) &= ({}^g F_x^{F,9})^2 + ({}^g F_y^{F,9})^2 - 10^2 = 0 & (j)
 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

If torques are not discussed, the origin of the coordinate system is not required, then the equations, (d), (e), and (f), in (8) are not used in the calculation.

The force stiffness matrix using the conventional adjustment method is ($\times 10^{-5}m^2$),

TABLE III
CONDITIONS IN THE ADJUSTMENT OF THE 3D MODEL

Force No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	
Condition in conventional adjustment	$F_x(N)$	10	5	6.1237	4.3301	2.5	8.2139	6.4085	8.3651	1.2940	1.3302	6.2750	1.5038	7.9124	3.0997	1.8301	1.6773	1.4454	4.9240
	$F_y(N)$	0	8.6602	6.1237	2.5	9.3301	3.8302	2.9883	2.2414	4.8296	7.5440	5.2654	0.8682	5.5403	1.4454	6.8301	0.4494	3.9713	0.8682
	$F_z(N)$	0	0	5	8.6602	2.5881	4.2261	7.0710	5	8.6602	6.4278	5.7357	9.8480	2.5881	9.3969	7.0710	9.8480	9.0630	8.6602
	$M_x(Nm)$	0	0.8660	0.1	0.05	0.08	0.1	0.05	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.08	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.08	0.06	0.12	0.1
	$M_y(Nm)$	0	-0.5	0.15	0.1	0.1	0.03	0.03	0.1	0.03	0.05	0.15	0.04	0.08	0.13	0.03	0.1	0.1	0.04
	$M_z(Nm)$	0	0	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.05	0.1	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.1	0.05	0.13	0.12	0.02	0.05
Objective function No.	1~3 a~c	4~5 d~e	6 f	7 g	8 h	9 i	10 j	11 k	12 l	13 m	14 n	15 o	16 p	17 q	18 r	19 s	20 t	21 u	
Condition in this paper's adjustment	$F(N)$	$F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$	$ F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$	$ F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$	$ F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$	$ F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$	$ F_x = 10$	$ F_y = 10$	$ F_z = 10$
	$M(Nm)$	$F_y = 0$	$F_z = 0$																

As shown in Fig. 14 (b) and TABLE II, twenty-one objective functions are employed in the adjustment of the 3D model.

The stiffness matrix using the conventional calibration method is ($\times 10^{-6}m^2$),

$$S_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 4.4958 & 1.5656 & 1.5736 & 4.5045 & -6.0738 & -6.0672 \\ 4.4058 & 6.1124 & -6.1045 & -4.4149 & 1.6903 & -1.6907 \\ 8.6597 & 8.2767 & 8.4191 & 8.6653 & 8.2058 & 8.3370 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$S_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.006433 & 1.289780 & -1.247521 \\ 3.733721 & -0.000404 & 3.733575 \end{bmatrix}$$

In fact, almost any optimization method can be used to calculate the nonlinear equations system (objective functions) (23), such as Deep-Learning, LSSVR fusion algorithm, etc.[15, 73-77]. Although these methods are usually unsuitable for the real-time calculation, they are suitable for the adjustment calculation especially when the number of object functions is very large or the object functions are very complex. Because the number of objective functions is not big in equation (23), a simple method, Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, is used in this paper.

The initial force stiffness matrix in this paper's adjustment is,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.000000 & 1.000000 & -1.000000 \\ 3.000000 & 0.000000 & 3.000000 \end{bmatrix}$$

The force stiffness matrix using this paper's adjustment method is,

$$S_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.006331 & 1.289757 & -1.247609 \\ 3.733707 & -0.000344 & 3.733511 \end{bmatrix}$$

The deviation matrix between the above two stiffness matrixes is,

$$\Delta S = |S_1 - S_2| = \begin{bmatrix} 0.000102 & 0.000023 & 0.000088 \\ 0.000014 & 0.000060 & 0.000063 \end{bmatrix}$$

The deviation matrix can be further decreased by decreasing the tolerance in the optimization.

The above result shows that the two stiffness matrixes are nearly identical.

The initial matrix for the calculation is,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4.0000 & 1.0000 & 1.0000 & 4.0000 & -6.0000 & -6.0000 \\ 4.0000 & 6.0000 & -6.0000 & -4.0000 & 1.0000 & -1.0000 \\ 8.0000 & 8.0000 & 8.0000 & 8.0000 & 8.0000 & 8.0000 \end{bmatrix}$$

The force stiffness matrix using this paper's adjustment method is,

$$S_4 = \begin{bmatrix} 4.4948 & 1.5610 & 1.5776 & 4.5068 & -6.0768 & -6.0661 \\ 4.4007 & 6.1079 & -6.1159 & -4.4194 & 1.6838 & -1.7012 \\ 8.6640 & 8.2798 & 8.4158 & 8.6616 & 8.2060 & 8.3360 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The deviation matrix between the above two stiffness matrixes is,

$$\Delta S = |S_3 - S_4|$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 0.0010 & 0.0046 & 0.0039 & 0.0023 & 0.0030 & 0.0011 \\ 0.0051 & 0.0044 & 0.0114 & 0.0044 & 0.0065 & 0.0105 \\ 0.0043 & 0.0030 & 0.0032 & 0.0037 & 0.0002 & 0.0010 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Apparently, the two force stiffness matrixes are nearly identical.

XI. CONCLUSION

The MAFS should be calibrated and adjusted statistically. The force magnitude can be employed as the stated reference in the force calibration of MAFS. The error sphere/ellipsoid is proposed to define the multi-axis force error and/or the multi-axis torque error. The force magnitude objective function and the force coordinate system objective function are proposed for the statistical adjustment in an optimization.

According to the simulation result, the force stiffness matrix calculated using this paper's adjustment method is nearly identical to the force stiffness matrix calculated using the conventional adjustment method.

The calibration and adjustment of the torque should be further studied. Besides, only an ideal MAFS is discussed in this paper, the calibration and adjustment of a more complex distributed multi-axis force sensing system should be further analyzed. In addition, the effect of the accuracy space and stress correlation coefficient on the calibration and adjustment should be further discussed.

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